

HEALTH AND WELLNESS TOURISM DEVELOPMENT ON GLOBAL MARKETS IN PANDEMIC

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Abstract

International crisis makes health and wellness tourism a powerful catalyst for the regional development in global economic competition. However, this was health and wellness tourism most affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. The article identifies the main economic consequences of COVID-19 for the field health and wellness tourism and for industries that depend on it. The state support is especially needed for the industry. The medical tourism market is now in crisis. This is due to the epidemiological health threats, a decrease in entrepreneurial activity, sharp drop in demand for both medical and tourism services because of decrease in the income of the population and the inability to use the existing infrastructure. The way out of this situation is possible only with the adoption of competent management decisions that could combine both the state support and provision for the most affected sectors of the national economy, and our own initiatives related to the introduction of changes in the organization and management of relevant business processes.

Keywords: COVID-19; Globalization; World Economy; Tourism Sector; Health and Wellness Tourism; Anti-Crisis Solutions.

DESENVOLVIMENTO DO TURISMO DE SAÚDE E BEM-ESTAR NOS MERCADOS GLOBAIS EM PANDEMIA**Resumo**

A crise internacional faz do turismo de saúde e bem-estar um poderoso catalisador para o desenvolvimento regional na competição econômica global. No entanto, o turismo de saúde e bem-estar foi um dos mais afetados pela pandemia da COVID-19. O artigo identifica as principais consequências econômicas da COVID-19 para o turismo de saúde e bem-estar no terreno e para as indústrias que dele dependem. O apoio do Estado é especialmente necessário para a indústria. O mercado do turismo médico está agora em crise. Isto deve-se às ameaças epidemiológicas à saúde, a uma diminuição da atividade empresarial, a uma queda acentuada da procura tanto de serviços médicos como de turismo como resultado da diminuição do rendimento da população e da incapacidade de utilizar as infraestruturas existentes. A saída para esta situação só é possível com a adoção de decisões de gestão competentes que possam combinar tanto o apoio estatal e a provisão para os setores mais afetados da economia nacional, como as nossas próprias iniciativas relacionadas com a introdução de mudanças na organização e gestão dos processos empresariais relevantes.

Palavras-chave: COVID-19; Economia Mundial; Globalização; Setor do Turismo; Turismo de Saúde e Bem-Estar; Soluções Anti-Crise.

DESARROLLO DEL TURISMO DE SALUD Y BIENESTAR EN LOS MERCADOS MUNDIALES EN PANDEMIA**Resumen**

La crisis internacional convierte al turismo de salud y bienestar en un poderoso catalizador del desarrollo regional en la competencia económica mundial. Sin embargo, el turismo de salud y bienestar fue el más afectado por la pandemia de COVID-19. El artículo identifica las principales consecuencias económicas de la COVID-19 para el campo del turismo de salud y bienestar y para las industrias que dependen de él. El apoyo estatal es especialmente necesario para la industria. El mercado del turismo médico está ahora en crisis. Esto se debe a las amenazas epidemiológicas para la salud, la disminución de la actividad empresarial, la fuerte caída de la demanda de servicios médicos y turísticos como resultado de la disminución de los ingresos de la población y la incapacidad de utilizar la infraestructura existente. La salida de esta situación sólo es posible con la adopción de decisiones de gestión competentes que puedan combinar tanto el apoyo y la provisión estatal a los sectores más afectados de la economía nacional, como nuestras propias iniciativas relacionadas con la introducción de cambios en la organización y gestión de los procesos empresariales pertinentes.

Palabras clave: COVID-19; Economía Mundial; Globalización; Sector Turístico; Turismo de Salud y Bienestar; Soluciones Contra la Crisis.

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1 INTRODUCTION

A significant number of scientific works by domestic and foreign authors are devoted to a segment of the leisure industry that is close, in terms of direction and consumer choice, to health tourism. At the same time, some authors tend to a methodological approach considering medical and health tourism as similar in functions and methods of organizing business activities, which comes into conflict with modern trends in the tourism and hospitality industry.

There is lack of the works dedicated to theoretical and methodological approaches to managing the interaction of participants in market relations in medical tourism, the development features and the identification of promising directions for the modernization of the medical tourism market in the post-crisis period. The above facts confirm the relevance and significance of the chosen topic, determine the purpose and objectives of the study (Hoyos & Wilson, 2020).

The article is aimed at analyzing the main forms and directions of socio-economic relationships among health tourism market participants and identifying promising ways to improve the intra-industry cooperation efficiency and network interaction in an unstable economic situation. The objectives of the article are to identify the main development stages of the health tourism market, considering the socio-economic characteristics of individual countries and regions, to study the key characteristics of the current development stage of the health tourism market under condition of a sharp deterioration in the epidemiological situation at the global level.

The study is focused the health tourism market, the features of its functioning and development in modern economic conditions, and possible ways of adapting to the consequences of the crisis. The special attention in the article is paid to the organizational and economic relations developing in the process of adaptation and ensuring sustainable interaction of participants in the medical tourism market to modern trends and prospects for transforming the sphere of recreation and tourism in crisis and the need to introduce innovative technologies.

The theoretical basis of this scenario are the work of domestic and foreign scientists in the field of recreation and tourism, the main provisions of Russian and foreign legal documentation on the organizing and managing the health tourism market in a pandemic.

Systematic and program-targeted approach, economic-statistical and heuristic methods of scientific research are the methodological basis of the study. The information base is represented by information and analytical data by official Russian and foreign statistics, the results of marketing and sociological research.

2 THEORETICAL REVIEW

Currently, the problems of adaptation of health and wellness and medical tourism are being investigated in the works of a sufficient number of authors. Conditionally, they can be classified into several main areas:

1) the conditions contributing to the restoration of the pace of medical and health tourism related to state support and market technologies of competition have been identified (Belyaeva, 2018; Han & Hwang, 2018; Kangas, 2010);

2) conclusions are drawn about the impact of global crises, including those caused by the pandemic and restrictions on the sphere of health and wellness and medical tourism (Carlsson-Szlezak et al., 2020; Gössling et al., 2020; Gretzel et al., 2020);

3) changes in supply and demand in the field of medical and health tourism, as well as global development trends caused by the pandemic (Iordache & Ciochina, 2014; Neretina et al., 2016; Vijaya & Baby, 2018).

At present, the problems of adaptation of recreational and medical tourism are studied by many authors. Conventionally, they can be grouped into several main areas:

1) studies dedicated to conditions conducive to the restoration of the of medical and health tourism associated with state support and market technologies of competition (Belyaeva, 2018; Han & Hwang, 2018; Kangas, 2010);

2) work with conclusions on the impact of global crises, including those caused by the pandemic and restrictions on the field of medical and health tourism (Carlsson-Szlezak et al., 2020; Gössling et al., 2020; Gretzel et al., 2020);

3) studies dedicated to changes in supply and demand in medical and health tourism, as well as global development trends caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (Iordache & Ciochina, 2014; Neretina et al., 2016; Vijaya & Baby, 2018).

3 METHODOLOGY

The study is based on methods of description, comparison, situational analysis, and modeling of socio-economic processes. Conclusions are resulting from theoretical analysis of publications on the adaptation and post-crisis development of health tourism. Statistical data and the experts' forecasts allow to understand the state of the art and restoration pace in tourism sector and considered sphere of services.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In modern conditions, health and wellness tourism is one of the leading and most dynamically developing sectors of national economies, associated with the need to restore the health of people who have recovered from the COVID-19.

Moreover, health tourism is part of the export-import transactions of world and regional trade in goods and services and is also a form of international interaction that launches integration processes in the global economy (Hopkins, 2021).

Tourism, the recognized economic phenomenon of the century for its high growth rates, contributes to the development of many countries, even those that at first glance are not attractive enough for this type of activity. An example is the desert territories of African states and the countries of the Middle East. It is impossible to deny the fact that it is tourism that contributes to a new type of spatial ties, reducing the risk of military conflicts, and helps in the cultural and technical enrichment of countries and peoples.

According to the UNWTO, its contribution to the world economy is 13%. Moreover, tourism accounts for 8% of total capital investment, 11% of global consumer spending, about 5% of all tax revenues and about 8% of world export income. It is important to note that in absolute terms, these indicators following only income from the export of oil, oil products and cars.

To date, the tourism industry continues to provide jobs to every tenth inhabitant of the planet (Iordache & Ciocina, 2014). This fact is also confirmed by the rather high share of growth in both the tourism sector (including the medical and health sector) and healthcare in GDP in 2019 (Table 1).

However, a serious blow to tourism came in mid-March 2020. So, for the period March-April of this year, the number of tourists traveling for medical and recreational purposes decreased by almost 60%.

Table 1. Growth dynamics of service sectors in the world market in 2019, %

Sector	GDP dynamics in 2019
Information and communication services	+4,8%
Travel and tourism	+3,9%
Healthcare	+3,7%
Financial services	+3,5
Wholesale and retail trade	+2,4

Source: Kreiner & Ram (2020).

Analyses of these indicators shows that in 2019, receipts from international medical and health tourism

amounted to approximately 1.5 USD trillion. However, the decrease in the number of tourists in May 2020 led to the loss of approximately 320 USD billion in exports. This value is three times higher than the losses suffered by this sector in 2009 during the crisis.

It is undeniable that the health tourism development depends on the pandemic spreading pace and the still uncertain duration of travel restrictions. (Morozov & Morozova, 2016). The COVID-19 in 2020 led to a decrease in the number of tourists by approximately 1.1 billion people, under the worst-case scenario and a loss of up to 1.2 USD trillion (Fig. 1).

Economic consequences of the crisis directly influenced not only tourism sector, it but the industries that depend on it, among which the most affected the hotel industry and transport (mainly air travel). For example, the tourism industry in Brazil suffered huge losses.

The consumption of hotel business services located on the territory of medical and recreational institutions was reduced by approximately 80%, all parks and tourist attractions were closed. It is predicted that in the absence of state support, they may lose about 7 USD billion. This is since the flow of tourists has decreased by 2 times. The figure 1 presents three main scripts for reducing revenue due to the COVID-19 pandemic: by 62%, 73% and 79% to 570, 400 and 310 USD billions, respectively.

At the end of March 2020, approximately 80,000 restaurants and 40,000 cafes were closed due to self-isolation in France. Approximately 40% of these institutions were focused for on tourists who took health and wellness trips. This process affected approximately 1 million employees who were classified as technical unemployed.

The situation in the UK was no less difficult. Approximately 75% of the employees of tourist hotels and cafes were placed on special leave for uncertain period, and about a third of jobs still are at long-term risk. In the USA, approximately 2 million hotel workers have been fired or placed on leave since the crisis began, and approximately 4 million hotel-dependent jobs have been lost. It is also predicted that up to 120 million people may lose their jobs in this field around the world.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, it has become common practice for employers not to lay off their employees, but to give them temporary unemployment benefits. Some employers together with unions develop strategies to avoid layoffs through reducing working hours. However, in some developing countries, the tourism industry makes up to 10% of the contribution to annual GDP and about 10% of all employees (Table 2).

Figure 1. Dynamics of receipts from international health and wellness tourism, in USD billions

Source: Kreiner & Ram (2020).

Table 2. Assessment of the contribution of health and wellness tourism to GDP and employment in 2019, %

A country	Industry contribution to GDP, %	Industry Contribution to Employment, %
Maldives	33%	13%
Seychelles	28%	27%
Bahamas	20%	28%
Philippines	13%	13%
Thailand	10%	9%
Iceland	9%	5%
Greece	8%	10%
Austria	7%	9%

Source: Kreiner & Ram (2020).

And if in developed countries the sectoral structure of national economies is more diversified, then for developing countries, the loss of income from the tourism business has become a serious challenge for maintaining social stability and was accompanied by a sharp increase in unemployment.

Among developing countries, island states such as the Seychelles, the Bahamas and the Maldives fall into the so-called risk group. In these countries, health and wellness tourism provides about a third of GDP and employment (Pecsvary, 2019). The ban on the entry for foreign tourists has also very negatively affected the economies of the Philippines and Thailand.

Analyzing the losses suffered by the transport sector, it can be seen that most air carriers and travel companies around the world are adjusting the staffing level of their employees, and many have frozen any kind of hiring in principle. In this case, key vacancies cannot be filled even after the end of the crisis (Neretina et al., 2016).

Many airports were closed and flights were cancelled, which has led to the temporary loss of over 10 million civil aviation jobs. Some airlines try to somehow attract passengers on board the aircraft. An

American company «Alaska Airlines» has taken quite bold measures.

Previously the company did not sell middle row tickets due to social distancing requirements. But now it offers to buy the entire row for the price of one ticket. Airline executives believe that this will allow them to return passengers on board. The economic problems that have arisen in the field of health and wellness tourism lead to a transformation of sustainable development goals (SDGs).

So, the impact of COVID-19 on tourism will inevitably lead to increasing poverty (SDG-1) and inequality (SDG-10). In turn it will minimize the efforts to preserve nature and culture. Analyzing the sustainable development goals, we can note that tourism itself is mentioned in such goals as decent work and economic growth (SDG-8) and responsible consumption and production (SDG-12).

Particularly, for women, representatives of rural communities, indigenous peoples and many other historically marginalized groups of the population, health tourism is a kind of integration tool that allows not only to earn income, but also to empower themselves. For example, the residents of small island developing states (SIDS) provide various SPA and Wellness services and take care of tourism infrastructure (Vertakova et al., 2013).

But in the current conditions this practice is not fully implemented, however, specialists working in health and wellness tourism are forced to focus on new quality and safety standards while providing health and recreational services. Industries, multiplicatively affected by tourism such as handicrafts, agriculture, international trade in the supply of food and beverages, etc., are also subject to a deep negative impact.

Health and wellness tourism has a serious impact on the climate and the environment, as it

requires more energy and fuel consumption, creating anthropogenic load on land resources.

The continuous development of health tourism and the transport services associated with it, increases the amount of greenhouse gas emissions. Tourism and air transportation create approximately 5% of all anthropogenic emissions, which is precisely what threatens the achievement of the targets set in the Paris Agreement.

The health and wellness tourism is an important source of financial income for the conservation of biodiversity, and make it important in a global context. about 7% of health and wellness tourism is directly related to wildlife, and this segment is increasing every year.

Thus, about 20 countries in Asia annually receive an income of approximately 150 million dollars in the form of fees for access to protected natural areas, which were also used as health tourism infrastructure. The current situation and the resulting closure of these protected areas have had a devastating impact not only on nature environment itself, but also on the very community that ensures the protection of these areas.

In some protected parks and areas located on the territory or near medical and recreational institutions, there has recently been an increase in the number of cases of poaching and looting. This was the result of a decrease in the number of tourists and employees of medical and recreational institutions (Turner, 2011). So, for example, in the Mara Nabisco nature reserve, located in Kenya, almost 50 rangers lost their earnings.

Moreover, the closure of other enterprises providing the functioning of the tourism infrastructure in the area has led to the fact that more than 600 Maasai families have lost their livelihoods. This clearly demonstrates the economic losses of some African countries and entails the destruction of biological diversity forming a kind of "core" of the natural tourist continent. This is because approximately 70% of the Kenya Wildlife Service's budget is funded by tourism activities. Thus, a decrease in tourism revenues and a reduction in the budget of national parks entail problems for public natural protected areas (Carlsson-Szlezak et al., 2020).

It is also noteworthy that, while visiting various health-improving institutions, modern tourists also tend to visit cultural heritage sites to get new emotions, which, as a rule, have a positive effect on the recovery process. However, almost 90% of museums around the world have closed their cultural heritage sites during the pandemic, and about 10% of them may never reopen.

The Network of European Museum Organizations estimates the revenue loss of museums located in European tourist areas at around 80%. Even as World Heritage Sites are slowly rebuilding with new health

and safety protocols, 2021 is forecast to see a significant drop in visitor numbers.

Thus, before the crisis caused by COVID-19, the global income of the cultural industry operating within the tourism industry was approximately 2,300 USD billion, and exports were 250 USD billion.

The COVID-19 development pace in 2021 gives reason to say that the recovery of the cultural industry's income to this level will not occur in 2022 either. Thus, the influence of health and wellness tourism on the world economy is becoming more and more obvious (Vijaya & Baby, 2018).

Therefore, "healthy" industry is extremely important, since it is tourism that occupies a special place in international foreign economic relations, forming a modern non-resource sector of the economy. However, the current unprecedented situation requires fundamentally new approaches, as well as decisive multi-level measures of state support. At this stage, the state should understand health tourism as one of the priority areas of economic policy.

Moreover, it should be interested in creating favorable conditions for the sustainable functioning of tourism, stimulating and supporting strategic directions, contributing to attractive image of destinations, ensuring the promotion of country's domestic tourism products at the international level. Support of this kind also implies that the key to tourism development is to consider well-being first and foremost, which depends on strong partnerships between national governments, private sectors, citizens and the international community (Kreiner & Ram, 2020).

In this case, planning should be more effective in terms of industry regulation (Karpova et al., 2018). Also, the state support for the industry should provide the creation of unique systems for measuring its effectiveness. Tools of this kind will allow us to assess the impact degree of the tourism sector on the economy, society and the environment. This, in turn, will provide proper strategic management for the industry development.

All of the above can be confirmed by the words of the Director General of the International Labor Office, which he said on April 24, 2020 at the extraordinary meeting of the Ministers for Tourism of the Group of Twenty. He is sure that "the priority task of the state is to ensure the survival of tourism enterprises through large-scale state support, without which they will die faster than the virus."

Summarizing all the above, we can conclude that, despite the rather difficult situation in which the sphere of health and wellness tourism found itself, it continues to strengthen its position. This, of course, affects the domestic and foreign tourism markets, which in turn

influences the development of countries and regions, and the structure of the economy.

Analyzing the impact of tourism on the global economy, it was found that tourism is able to develop local infrastructure, create additional jobs, and have a stimulating effect on the service industries. Moreover, historically, tourism has been able to quickly adapt to changing market needs, innovate and recover from global shocks (Gretze et al., 2020).

Confirming the above, it is advisable to refer to the historical experience of the industry development, focusing on the fact that it was able to quickly recover both after the crisis of 1929 and after the end of World War II, after September 11, 2001, as well as after financial crises of 2009 and 2014. This gives grounds to assume that in the near future a gradual recovery of the industry will begin, which in the future will be able to create fundamentally new competitive tourism products.

During the pandemic, several state support measures were announced for the tourism sector, and most respondents applied for it. The deferral of taxes and obligations on canceled tours and subsidizing salary costs were the most requested measures according to the survey.

Additionally, in August 2020, a cashback program for the purchase of domestic tours in Russia was announced. About 7 rubles were attracted for one 1 ruble of the funds used from the program budget. Tax incentives include bankruptcy moratoriums, tax sanctions, audits, tax holidays, tax exemptions on SME subsidies, suspension of collection measures, extension of tax payment deadlines, accounting for non-working days for tax purposes.

Subsidizing operating expenses includes subsidizing SMEs' access to loans at a reduced rate, payments under leasing agreements for shipping companies, subsidies for tour operators to recover losses associated with air transportation (Vijaya & Baby, 2018). Support in obtaining financing includes subsidizing an interest rate, providing a guarantee for a loan, providing an opportunity to restructure loans, etc.

Deferrals and incentives for rental payments are established not only for the tourism industry, for this, in the general case, it is necessary to conclude an additional agreement with the landlord. The deferment for non-tax payments is established by the RF GD dated April 24, 2020 No. 570, it is valid for up to 6 months and is available to companies registered in the of SMEs.

Several information resources have been created for consulting – a guide of the Government of the Russian Federation on support measures, a hotline, SMEs support measures to navigator by Ministry of Economic Development of Russia, service “SME

Corporation” and others. The provision of grants and subsidies includes interest-free loans for salary payments, salary grants, urgent needs, utility bills, etc.

Other measures include access to the tour operator's personal liability fund, the contribution of outbound tour operators to the reserve fund of the Association of Tour Operators of Russia for 2020, refunds in case of cancellation and rescheduling of events, and reduction of insurance premiums for SMEs.

To overcome the COVID-19 crisis consequences, governments have taken both comprehensive measures to restore the entire economy and special measures aimed at supporting the tourism industry directly (Kangas, 2010).

The main groups of measures aimed at restoring the tourism industry are the following.

First, it is fiscal policy, namely, tax exemption or tax deferral, programs to support SMEs or individual tourism market participants such as airlines, investment programs aimed at mitigating the impact of the pandemic.

Secondly, it is the policy in the field of employment and training: increasing the amount of unemployment benefits, training workers and developing their digital skills, promoting the digital transformation of the tourism business, financial support for training programs and professional retraining of workers (Żegleń et al., 2019).

Thirdly, this is a public-private partnership: the creation of solidarity funds by governments, together with interested representatives of the private sector, to restore the tourism industry.

Fourth, it is market research: developing intelligent data processing systems to track trends in the tourism industry, as well as providing participants in the tourism industry with access to real-time data to better respond to the consequences of COVID-19; establishment of tourism coordinating committees, research and surveys to adjust marketing strategies.

Fifth, it is monetary policy: exemption from loan payments or their deferment, the introduction of special credit lines, new lending schemes and loan guarantees for tourism enterprises (Seow et al., 2017).

Sixth, it is a policy aimed at resuming tourism flows and supporting domestic tourism: opening external borders with other countries, developing initiatives to develop new products and provide special discounts in marketing and advertising campaigns for the domestic tourism development (Gössling et al., 2020).

Let's consider examples of anti-crisis solutions for the restoration of the tourism industry in several countries around the world.

In Spain a special certificate was approved. It is the tourist services quality sign, which market participants can receive after checking their activities by an independent organization and use to confirm compliance with all sanitary and epidemiological safety measures. The number of tariffs that are charged to airlines when their planes land at Spanish airports has been reduced.

In France, new conditions were introduced for canceling bookings of tourist products: instead of a refund for a booking, customers were offered to issue a credit memo for the right to purchase another service in the future for an equivalent amount. This allowed the organizations of the tourist market to avoid a rapid outflow of funds. To support domestic tourism in the country, an active advertising campaign was launched on social networks, during which, among other things, it was shown how influencers travel around the country (Dwyer & Alison, 2019).

In Israel, the Ministry of Tourism has organized a comprehensive program of professional webinars and online courses for travel agents, tour operators, tour guides and other participants in the tourism industry. The program includes practical expert advice on dealing with the crisis and planning activities for the post-coronavirus period. The Ministry of Tourism and local governments have released virtual tours of the country's tourist spots and attractions to fuel demand and remind customers of delayed tours (Kim & Chr.Arcodia, 2019).

China has saved tour guide jobs, provided them with free distance learning programs, eliminated annual tax payments and extended the deadlines for accreditation and renewal of professional certifications. The infrastructure of the most visited tourist destinations and resorts has been improved. The Ministry of Culture and Tourism has selected 346 construction projects for 2020 to be financed from the state budget (Belyaeva, 2018).

In Australia, additional government support for the Australian Tourism Exchange (ATE) was provided in the amount of AU\$6.5 million. ATE is Australia's largest annual tourism business event, bringing together and networking opportunities for tourism industry representatives from Australia and around the world.

The financial support allowed the organizers of the event, among other things, to cancel the participation fee for market players and thus further encourage them to attend ATE this year.

An interactive online map of Australia has been developed. It provides information on the COVID-19 restrictions in each state, includes additional guidance, the latest travel data and other useful information resources (Han & Hwang, 2018).

5 CONCLUSIONS

Thus, despite the rather difficult situation, health and wellness tourism continues to strengthen its position. This, of course, affects the state of the domestic and foreign tourism markets, and therefore the countries and regions development and the economy structure as a whole. Analyzes of tourism impact on the global economy shows that tourism is able to contribute to local infrastructure development, create additional jobs, and have a stimulating effect on the service industries. Moreover, historically, tourism has been able to quickly adapt to changing market needs, innovate and recover from global shocks.

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Table 1. CRediT author statement

Term	Definition	Author
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	+
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	+
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	+
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	+
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	+
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	+
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	+
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	+
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	+
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre- or post-publication stages	+
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	+
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team	+
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	+
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	+

Source: adapted from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

Processo Editorial / Editorial Process / Proceso Editorial

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